

Benchmarking Legume Yield Components

Problem

Crops face limitations throughout their development which mean they don't reach their full yield potential. It is not always clear when during the season these limitations occurred, making it difficult for growers to know which management practices should be improved in future years.

Solution

The Pulse Yield Enhancement Networks (UK) have developed a practical method to assess yield in dry-harvested field peas and faba beans. This method uses simple measurements taken after harvest to understand how crop development affected final yield. The approach is based on measuring the yield components that contribute to final seed yield:

- the number of seeds produced, and
- the average weight of individual seeds.

Benefits

By comparing or “benchmarking” these measurements with published data, or new data collected from relevant farms, growers can identify whether yield was mainly limited early or late in the season. This helps growers focus management changes where they are most likely to improve yield and farm profitability.

Practical recommendation

Final seed yield is determined by two main components: seed number, and seed weight (Figure 1). Yield limitations can be broadly grouped into two types:

- “**Sink limitation**” occurs when the crop produces too few seeds or potential seed size is limited. This is linked to the number and potential size of the reproductive units. For dry harvested field pea and faba bean in temperate conditions, this usually occurs before or shortly after flowering caused by e.g. poor plant establishment, low numbers of flowering or reproductive nodes and flower or young seed abortion (e.g. from heat or drought stress).

Applicability box

Theme

Optimising pulse productivity

Keywords

Yield components; sink limitation; source limitation; benchmarking

Context

Arable rotations

Application time

End of season as a reflection of management approach

Required time

1 hour per field

Period of impact

Between years

Equipment

Seed moisture meter, weighing balance precision to nearest gram

Best in

Faba bean and dry harvested peas

Figure 1. Diagram showing that final seed yield is made up of seed number and seed weight. Seed yield per unit area (g/m^2) can be calculated by dividing yield (t/ha) by 100. Dividing seed yield (g/m^2) by the average individual seed weight (g) provides an estimate of the number of seeds produced per square metre. Diagram: (ADAS).

- “Source limitation” occurs when the crop cannot supply enough resources to fill the seeds properly. This is commonly linked to reduced photosynthesis, poor canopy longevity and stress during the seed-filling period.
- The number of seeds per unit area developed in a crop is a good indicator of sink size. The final weight of a seed is a good indicator of source size.
- If seed yield (t/ha) and seed weight is known, then a calculation can be made to estimate seeds/m². Seed yield (t/ha) can be expressed as g/m² by dividing by 100.
- Average seed weight can be measured by counting a number of seeds (ca. 100), weighing the sample and then dividing the weight by the number of seeds in the sample (Figure 2). It is important that the seed yield and seed weight are both expressed at the same moisture content (15 %; See Practice Abstract: Accurate Measurement of Grain Crop Yields).
- If benchmarking shows:
 - fewer seeds than expected → sink limitation; or,
 - smaller seeds than expected → source limitation.

Figure 2. Faba beans being counted to calculate average individual Seed Weight, which is expressed as the weight of 1000 seeds or thousand seed weight (g) typically at 15% moisture content. Photo: (ADAS).

Then additional yield components (such as plants per m², pods per shoot, or seeds per pod) can be examined to identify which stage of crop growth was most affected (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Diagram illustrating how seed number (seeds/m²) and seed filling (seed weight) are influenced by several crop growth components, including plant population, shoot number, pods per shoot, and seeds per pod. Diagram: ADAS, adapted from BASF Bean Growth Guide.

Further information

- For more information on pulse crop growth and development and when yield components are formed throughout the season, see the BASF [Pea](#) and [Bean](#) Growth and development guides.
- For more information on which yield components are associated with high crop performance, see analysis summaries from the [Pea](#) and [Bean](#) Yield Enhancement Networks & [White et al., \(2022\)](#).

About this practice abstract

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